

Anaerobic digestion for sustainability in waste (water) treatment and reuse

Key words – anaerobic , methanogenesis , reactors , waste treatment

Introduction

Anaerobic digestion is a biological process that occurs in the absence of oxygen , where microorganisms breakdown organic matter in to simpler compounds such as methane CH₄ and carbon dioxide (CO₂) . It takes place in various natural and engineered environments , including digestive systems of animals, landfills and anaerobic digesters .

Anaerobic digestion can be used to treat waste water from various sources , such as wastewater treatment plants , agricultural residues , food waste , and animal manure . this helps to reduce waste volume , control odor , and produce energy. The process of anaerobic digestion generates nutrient-rich digestate , which can be used as a valuable fertilizer for agriculture.

Anaerobic digestion can be incorporated as a component of wastewater treatment processes to treat organic waste present in waste water and generate biogas .

01. Pre-treatment

In water treatment , anaerobic digestion is generally proceeded by preliminary treatment processes , such as screening and grit removal , to remove large particles and debris that may cause clogging or damage to the anaerobic digester.

02. Anaerobic reactor

A specialized anaerobic digester , often referred to as an anaerobic reactor , is utilized for the anaerobic digestion process. Wastewater , along with additional organic substrates if necessary, is introduced in to the reactor . the anaerobic reactor is a sealed vessel or tank where microorganisms breakdown the organic matter in the absence of oxygen.

03. Anaerobic digestion

Within the anaerobic reactor , the wastewater undergoes the series of steps involved in anaerobic digestion: hydrolysis , acidogenesis , acetogenesis and methanogenesis . anaerobic bacteria and archaea in the reactor convert complex organic compounds in to

simpler compounds such as volatile fatty acids , alcohols , acetic acid , hydrogen , carbon dioxide and methane . the methane produced is captured and collected as biogas.

04. Biogas utilization

The biogas produced during anaerobic digestion can be utilized as an energy resource. It can be used for electricity generation , heating , or as a vehicle fuel after purification and removal of impurities such as moisture, hydrogen sulfide, and other trace gases. The utilization of biogas makes the process more sustainable and helps to reduce reliance on fossil fuels.

05. Solids separation

After anaerobic digestion, the remaining solids, known as digestate or sludge, go through future treatment processes for separation and dewatering. Mechanical methods such as centrifugation or filtration can be used to separate the liquid effluent from the solid digestate.

06. Post-treatment

The liquid effluent from the anaerobic digestion process, known as anaerobic effluent , still contains some dissolved organic matter and nutrients. It may undergo additional treatment processes , such as anaerobic treatment or disinfection, to further remove any remaining pollutants or microorganisms before being discharged or recycled.

The process of anaerobic digestion and methane fermentation is multistage. Complex polymers and chemicals in biomass degrade to lower molecular weight intermediates , which are then transformed to methane and carbon dioxide. It entails intricate microbiological changes.

The rate at which biogas is formed is determined by temperature (a higher temperature usually result in a faster rate) and the composition of the substrate to be digested. Crop residues and municipal solid waste , for example, produce biogas more slowly than sewage sludge and animal manure. Changes in temperature, PH , feedstock composition , toxins in feedstock and other factors can cause a build up of acids that impede the methane generating bacteria. In general, anaerobic digestion systems perform best when the temperature and feedstock are kept consistent. When a digester is first begun , the bacterial composition is rarely optimal. However, if the feedstock and operating circumstances remain consistent , natural selection occurs until the bacteria best suited to metabolize the feedstock prevail. Biogas production begins within a few days , but total stability can take several months.

The procedure can be carried out on a huge scale indefinitely as long as the critical fermentation parameters are kept within acceptable limits and fermentable material is available. With the probable exception of lignin and keratin, almost any biomass feedstock composition is appropriate, which have low biodegradability.

Bacteriology of anaerobic digestion

The severe anaerobic conditions needed for the anaerobic digestion process result in a bacterial fermentation involving at least four groups of bacteria that work together to completely break down complex organic biopolymers into CO₂ and CH₄. In order for bacteria to produce energy for development, substrates must typically be biochemically oxidized without the presence of any air.

This is often accomplished by completely removing oxygen and then using more hydrogen. The primary driving force behind anaerobic digestion is the demand for adequate hydrogen acceptor for the other bacteria, which serves as a regulating system for overall fermentation.

Hydrogen transfer reactions in anaerobic conditions

The basic method of producing hydrogen using microbes is widely understood. Pyruvic acid is metabolized to hydrogen and other metabolic end product by certain microbes. Some species use biomass fermentation intermediates as hydrogen donors.

Methanogenic bacteria

Using the 16s ribosomal RNA fingerprinting method and the substrates they utilize for growth and methanogenesis, the methanogens have been split into three categories. A surprising divergence between the methanogenes and other bacteria was discovered. Many species have been isolated, investigated in pure culture, and taxonomically identified and categorized. The following species are a few of note:

Methanobacterium formicicum, *Methanobacterium bryantii*, *Methanobacterium thermoautotrophicum*, *Methanobrevibacter ruminantium*, *Methanobacterium arboriphilus*, *Methanococcus vanniellii*, *Methanospirillum hungatei* and *Methanosarcina*. Most methanogens – if not all can produce and grow from methane using hydrogen and CO₂. Methane is produced when carbon dioxide is converted to hydrogen, with hydrogen serving as the electron donor. In this way, facultative autotrophs make up the majority of methanogens.

Acetate , methanol , methylamines , and formals are some other resources that some species can employ for growth and methane synthesis.

Factors effecting the anaerobic process.

The widespread use of the anaerobic method has been partly constrained by the notion that it is unstable and unreliable. In order to improve anaerobic process technology , it is necessary to have a deeper understanding of the variables affecting the stability of the underlying biological process.

The most fastidious methanogens are the most susceptible to upset the ideal conditions and range for anaerobic digestions have been studied by many investigations , but there is not always agreement , process in stability is typically indicated by a rapid increase in the concentration of the volatile acids with a concurrent decrease in the methane gas production. This can be due to the fact that their research were carried out utilizing various feed materials and procedures. Single sets of parameters do not appear to be applicable in all circumstances since the microbial regime that exists depends on the nature and composition of the substrate material. Lack of acclimation times may be the cause of numerous process failures. It has been claimed that it takes the microorganisms more than 5 weeks to acclimatize to a substrate, but once they have demonstrated remarkable stability in the face of stressful situations.

Methodology

The sample which was collected from poultry farm industry , feed to the anaerobic digester. Before feed into that PH and temperature was measured.

The anaerobic digester that used to do the poultry waste water treatment

Results

Date	time	Volume rate	Filter rate	Reactor 01 inlet PH	Reactor 01 inlet HRT	Reactor 01 inlet cod	Pump 01 rate	Pump 02 rate	Reactor 01 outlet PH	Reactor 02 outlet PH	Decreased rate	Gas emission reactor 01	Gas emission reactor 02	Remarks
2023.08.10	10a.m	1750 ml	1.67 l ^d ⁻¹	6.6 25°C	2.4	4570	5	9	7.0 29.2°C	7.9 29.5°C	1225ml	144	250	Gas collected
2023.08.11	10a.m	1200 ml	2.5	6.3 29.8°C			5.5	10	7.1 30.2°C	8.1 29.4°C		119	241	
2023.08.14	10a.m	1000 ml	2.1	6.7 29.4°C			5.5	10	6.9 29.2°C	7.9 29.4°C	1.6 liter per day	116	241	Refilled the sample
2023.08.15	10a.m	3000 ml	2.5	6.3 29.8°C		513	6	10	6.9 27.8°C	7.6 28°C	1.25 liter per day	99	236	Gas collected

Collected water
sample after anaerobic digestion

Conclusions

The development and utilization of high rate anaerobic bioreactors is important to the successful application of anaerobic digestion technology to the treatment of industrial wastewater. This is because enormous amounts of effluent must be treated and ideally constructed bioreactors can reduce treatment time and increase treatment efficiency, resulting in a reduced overall treatment cost. The use of high rate reactors has increased awareness of anaerobic digestion as a cost effective and efficient environmental technique. High rate reactors satisfy the two characteristics listed below :

- Under high organic loading levels, viable sludge retention is high

- Good interaction between the biomass and the entering wastewater, the reactors size is minimized and the process energy requirements are minimal.

References

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